

RESEARCH ARTICLE

A Sense of Lassitude and Unease in the Speaker of *Sonnet LXVI*

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Accepted version published on 1st May 2026

 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19952940>

ABSTRACT

This paper examines the sense of lassitude and divestment of joy in Sonnet LXVI. It represents the fallen world of Shakespeare across his dramatic and lyrical form. The speaker has disaffection towards the hellish world. The speaker feels a kind of alienation and distortion which overstate him as unchosen. The sonnet functions as a critique of society and the loss of values. Like his other plays, this sonnet overemphasises Christian values like humility and endurance. The captain of greed and profit governs the world. The speaker remains ethical and allows his feelings to be verbalised. He is too pure to die and too innocent to rebel. The tone of the poem is observational and judgmental. Love is the only source of redemption and protection in the fallen world. The sonnet starts with a cry for death, a pathway to escape the pain, but ends with a tussle of questions on death.

Keywords: Self-slaughtering, fallen world, endurance, humility

FULL RESEARCH PAPER

Introduction

Sonnet is one of the oldest forms of poetry. It has travelled widely across different countries. According to Wordsworth, the sonnet functioned as a myrtle leaf, a traditional form used to celebrate the purity of love. Wyatt, Surrey, Shakespeare, Spenser, Donne, and Herbert unlocked their hearts. If we examine diachronically, we see that writers like Milton, Shelley, Brooke, and Auden used to critique society and advocate for peace and freedom. Shakespeare wrote 154 sonnets, published in 1609 by Thomas Thorpe. Shakespeare has used the sonnet as a form for philosophical argumentation and approbation. Sonnet LXVI is a critique of society and the loss of value. It describes a fallen world full of bleakness and moral corruption. The speaker shows a sense of lassitude and a remarkably egalitarian tone rather than a rebellious one. The speaker is frustrated and tired of a broken, savage world full of dishonesty and greed. The sonnet has painful contrariness, which brings anxiety and illness in the speaker's mind. The poem follows the rhyme scheme abab cdcd efef gg and is written in iambic pentameter. "Upon every other stage the universal agent is love, by whose power all good and evil is distributed and every action quickened or retarded." (Johnson 2758)

Sonnet LXVI

In the fallen world, the only universal agent is love, which affirms life to the speaker. Similarly, in his sonnets, love dominates and controls everything. They choose life rather than death because of love and friendship. The sonnets open with lamentation for the fall of the people and world. The sonnet is not directly addressed to the fair youth, but a kind of triangulation between the speaker, the reader, and the fair youth. It is a rhetoric of praise and blame.

Tired with all these, for restful death I cry:

As to behold desert a beggar born.

(Shakespeare 29)

The sonnet opens with a declaration and a desire to die. The speaker feels weary and tired of seeing injustice in which the deserving suffer while the undeserving are rewarded. Here, the word *deserted* means people who rely on gods, who strip away comfort and are faithful. It's a fallen world, where they are unrewarded, and the speaker is longing for restful death. The speaker desires death to escape pain and

suffering. The poet has used a colon mark to list the things that compel self-slaughter. The speaker's melancholy resembles Antonio in *The Merchant of Venice*.

These griefs and losses have so battered me.

(Shakespeare 99)

And needy nothing trimmed in jollity,

And purest faith unhappily forsworn,

And gilded honour shamefully misplaced,

(Shakespeare 29)

The speaker feels baffled by the complexity of life and hollow affluence. Those who are worthless are decorated with jollity. People with purest faith and loyalty are forsworn and broken. The poet is using *Gilded honour* to critique people who misuse power and shine with dishonesty. The poet uses anaphora, or repetition, to evoke a strong emotion or to compare ideas. Similarly, William Blake's *London* uses anaphora.

In every cry of every Man,

In every infant's cry of fear,

In every voice: in every ban

(Blake line 5-7)

In the sonnet LXVI, it works as a removal of hope and relief and tolling of bells. The loss of values is disappointing to the speaker. The negligence of his lover also affects the speaker. Similarly, Antonio in *The Merchant of Venice* suffered due to Bassanio's negligence and the loss of his ships, while remaining faithful and loyal to them. A society that is corrupted and bleak, lovers who fail to see, brings pain for the speaker. As a result, the speaker is tempted towards death and looks for relief. He is wounded by society and his lover. He is unchosen.

Well, gaoler, on; pray God Bassanio come

To see me pay his debt, and then I care not.

(Shakespeare 99)

According to Vendler, Shakespeare juxtaposes fair and foul through adjectives and prefixes. For example, *purest faith and forsworn, gilded honour and misplaced, and right perfection and disgraced*. Similarly, in his plays, he juxtaposed ideal and wicked, loss of certain values in a fallen world. Antonio, with purest faith and maiden virtue

forsworn and strumpeted. The speaker feels a kind of abjection towards society and complains about the loss. Portio, *needy, nothing* has been trimmed in celebration, and he is relinquished.

The pangs of despised love, the law's delay.

(Shakespeare 91)

The speaker is blaming the sinners of will for the fall. It alludes to the parable of The Rich man and Lazarus. The rich man who wears purple clothes symbolises royalty and high status. The Rich man ate the best food and held a feast and lived with ease, but Lazarus, a poor, weak and helpless, starving, lived with difficulty. The Rich man saw him every day but didn't help him. They died; Lazarus lived comfortably after death, while the rich man suffered. Antonio and the speaker are tempted towards death for relief and comfort. The complexity of life is that they are willing to protect and save their love, but still forsworn. As a result, it creates a sense of abjection.

And strength by limping, sway disabled.

And art made tongue-tied by authority,

And folly, doctor-like, controlling skill,

And simple truth miscall'd simplicity,

And the good-attending captive is ill.

(Shakespeare 29)

The speaker finds it difficult to live in a world of corruption and greed. The speaker is criticising the sinners of flesh. The sin of flesh is not only about conquering the body but is dominated by wildness, ego, and pride. People desire dominance like Cain. They cannot tolerate the rectitude of people. They don't even repent for the sin but move uprightly. Similarly, Shylock desires a pound of flesh, governed by wildness and ego.

His rigorous course, but since he stands obdurate,

And that no lawful means can carry me

Out of his envy's reach.

(Shakespeare 110)

According to Vendler, the use of anaphora shows what art looks like when it is tongue-tied. This line *and the folly (doctor-like) controlling skill are significant because they mention* the sinners of intellect, who misuse their knowledge for power. He is naming criminals and the rule of vice over virtue. *Doctor-like* can be interpreted as people like Doctor Faustus, who used knowledge to gain power and rule over others. They are governed by cruel passion and destroy the world.

*And simple truth miscalled simplicity,
And a captive good attending captain, I'll.*

(Shakespeare 29)

Simple truths, like honesty, kindness, and faithfulness, are mischaracterised or rejected by them. Similarly, Shylock, who misused the bond for revenge against Antonio.

A goodly apple rotten at the heart.

(Shakespeare 32)

The bond was for mutual respect and friendship rather than to take revenge against Antonio. Sinners of Will, Flesh, and Intellect makes the speaker weary. The complexity of life is that they are rewarded, but the speaker is neglected by society and his love. The speaker is asking analytical questions, such as 'What should we do?' And what is wrong with the world? The speaker is staging devastation and appealing to readers to feel his loss. He argues that power and wealth without humility are destructive for society.

For the speaker of this sonnet, death seems to be a peaceful solution. The couplet ends with a question.

*Tired with all these, from those would I be gone,
Save that to die, I leave my love alone.*

(Shakespeare 29)

There's use of the refrain, a literary technique that involves the repetition of a word, phrase or line in a verse. The speaker is willing to self-slaughter, but his love pulls him back to life. *Save that* means expectation, or but in the Elizabethan context. He desires to die but worries about his lover. This is a platonic form of love, selfless love concerned for his beloved's welfare. In a world of corruption and greed, love is the only pure and uncorrupted motivation to restore his life. The battle is between his death vs love and duty. The world destroys him, but he endures humility and

friendship rather than self-slaughter. His love for the young man stops his departure. Antonio's cause of death is from outside, and he never desired to end his own life.

I am a tained wether of the flock,

Meetest for death.

(Shakespeare 115)

The speaker is baffled in the world of corruption, struggling to interpret the cause, but ends without a clear answer for who is responsible for the fall of the world. But in the case of the speaker of sonnet LXVI, death is an act of absolute agency, where he has the freedom to choose death or not. For the speaker, death is internal. Death, which seems to be his friend, is an enemy. Self-slaughtering in Christianity is a sin, transgressing Christian theology. It will break divine order or law. He is too pure to die or to self-slaughter. The rhetorical question is whether, if self-slaughtered, he will be a sinner of flesh, will, and intellect. He is pure but unrewarded, living in an uncompromising world. The poet is asking: if the speaker had self-slaughtered, would his purity survive?

And the worst friend and enemy is but death.

(Brooke line-14)

But suffering is to be endured rather than ending it. But the speaker's purity forbids self-slaughtering, and love functions as a redemptive force. The speaker treats death as an enemy who will erase his honour and himself. He is choosing the worst friend; his love and life are an act of endurance and humility.

Conclusion

The speaker's conflict was like Hamlet's: live or die. To endure or erase himself. He was baffled about whether to be Judas or Peter. Judas goes through pain and feels the need to erase himself, and Peter, who goes through pain but endures life and stays alive even without certainty and answers. The speaker feels the same lassitude and unease as Judas, but he acts like Peter, with endurance and humility. He is not tempted by death but endures life. Sonnet 66 reflects that Shakespeare is highly imaginative, philosophical, and religious. His openness to the complexities and mysteries of life. Imagination is a mode of combining religion and philosophy. He uses sonnets to intersect with each other. In the end, he is neither a philosopher nor a priest, but a fusion of the two. Sonnet 66 functions as a social critique and presents a cause-and-effect argument.

Author Contributions: All authors have contributed equally to this work. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: The data sharing policy does not apply to this article.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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